

THE COLD WAR OF 1946-1991 AND ITS CONSEQUENCES

Asatov Alibek

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Student of the 305 th group of the Faculty of History

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516275>

Abstract.

Looking at the world as a whole, the drift for many decades has been not towards anarchy but towards the reimposition of slavery... James Burnham's theory has been much discussed, but few people have yet considered its ideological implications—that is, the kind of world-view, the kind of beliefs, and the social structure that would probably prevail in a state which was at once unconquerable and in a permanent state of "cold war" with its neighbours.

Keywords. Cold war, factor, economic, technological, ideological, democratic republic.

The Cold War was a period of geopolitical tension between the United States and the Soviet Union and their respective allies, the Western Bloc and the Eastern Bloc, between 1945 and 1991. The term cold war is used because there was no large-scale fighting directly between the two superpowers, but they each supported opposing sides in major regional conflicts known as proxy wars. The conflict was based on the ideological and geopolitical struggle for global influence by these two superpowers, following their roles as the Allies of World War II that led to victory against Nazi Germany and Imperial Japan in 1945.[2] Aside from the nuclear arms race and conventional military deployment, the struggle for dominance was expressed via indirect means, such as psychological warfare, propaganda campaigns, espionage, far-reaching embargoes, sports diplomacy, and technological competitions like the Space Race. The Cold War began shortly after the end of World War II, started a gradual winding down with the Sino-Soviet split between the Soviets and the People's Republic of China in 1961, and ended with the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991.

Soviet territorial demands to Turkey regarding the Dardanelles in the Turkish Straits crisis and Black Sea border disputes were also a major factor in increasing tensions.[103][96] In September, the Soviet side produced the Novikov telegram, sent by the Soviet ambassador to the US but commissioned and "co-authored" by Vyacheslav Molotov; it portrayed the US as being in the grip of monopoly capitalists who were building up military capability "to prepare the conditions for winning world supremacy in a new war".[104] On 6

¹ Breslauer, George W. (2002). Gorbachev and Yeltsin as Leaders. Cambridge University Press.

September 1946, James F. Byrnes delivered a speech in Germany repudiating the Morgenthau Plan (a proposal to partition and de-industrialize post-war Germany) and warning the Soviets that the US intended to maintain a military presence in Europe indefinitely. As Byrnes stated a month later, "The nub of our program was to win the German people ... it was a battle between us and Russia over minds ..." In December, the Soviets agreed to withdraw from Iran after persistent US pressure, an early success of containment policy.

By 1947, US president Harry S. Truman was outraged by the perceived resistance of the Soviet Union to American demands in Iran, Turkey, and Greece, as well as Soviet rejection of the Baruch Plan on nuclear weapons.[107] In February 1947, the British government announced that it could no longer afford to finance the Kingdom of Greece in its civil war against Communist-led insurgents.[108] In the same month, Stalin conducted the rigged 1947 Polish legislative election which constituted an open breach of the Yalta Agreement. The US government responded to this announcement by adopting a policy of containment,[109] with the goal of stopping the spread of communism. Truman delivered a speech calling for the allocation of \$400 million to intervene in the war and unveiled the Truman Doctrine, which framed the conflict as a contest between free peoples and totalitarian regimes. American policymakers accused the Soviet Union of conspiring against the Greek royalists in an effort to expand Soviet influence even though Stalin had told the Communist Party to cooperate with the British-backed government.(The insurgents were helped by Josip Broz Tito's Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia against Stalin's wishes.)Enunciation of the Truman Doctrine marked the beginning of a US bipartisan defense and foreign policy consensus between Republicans and Democrats focused on containment and deterrence that weakened during and after the Vietnam War, but ultimately persisted thereafter. Moderate and conservative parties in Europe, as well as social democrats, gave virtually unconditional support to the Western alliance, while ²European and American Communists, financed by the KGB and involved in its intelligence operations, adhered to Moscow's line, although dissent began to appear after 1956. Other critiques of the consensus policy came from anti-Vietnam War activists, the Campaign for Nuclear Disarmament, and the anti-nuclear movement.

While most historians trace the origins of the Cold War to the period immediately following World War II, some argue that it began with the 1917

² Chandler, David (2000). *Brother Number One: A Political Biography of Pol Pot*, Revised Edition. Chiang Mai, Thailand: Silkworm Books.

October Revolution in the Russian Republic when the Bolsheviks overthrew the Russian Provisional Government. In World War I, the British, French and Russian Empires had composed the major Allied Powers from the start, and the US joined them as a self-styled Associated Power in April 1917. After the Bolsheviks' seizure of power, the bloody Red Terror was initiated to shut down all opposition, both perceived and real.[14] In December, the Bolsheviks signed an armistice with the Central Powers, though by February 1918, fighting had resumed. In March, the Soviets ended involvement in the war and signed the separate peace Treaty of Brest-Litovsk. As a result, German armies advanced rapidly across the borderlands. The Allies responded with an economic blockade against the new Russian regime.[15] In the eyes of some Allies, Russia now was helping Germany to win the war by freeing up a million German soldiers for the Western Front[16] and by relinquishing much of Russia's food supply, industrial base, fuel supplies, and communications with Western Europe. According to historian Spencer Tucker, the Allies felt, "The treaty was the ultimate betrayal of the Allied cause and sowed the seeds for the Cold War. With Brest-Litovsk the spectre of German domination in Eastern Europe threatened to become reality, and the Allies now began to think seriously about military intervention," and proceeded to step up their "economic warfare" against the Bolsheviks.[15] Some Bolsheviks saw Russia as only the first step, planning to incite revolutions against capitalism in every western country, but the need for peace with Germany led Soviet leader Vladimir Lenin away from this position. In late February 1946, George F. Kennan's "Long Telegram" from Moscow to Washington helped to articulate the US government's increasingly hard line against the Soviets, which would become the basis for US strategy toward the Soviet Union for the duration of the Cold War. The telegram galvanized a policy debate that would eventually shape the Truman administration's Soviet policy.[95] Washington's opposition to the Soviets accumulated after broken promises by Stalin and Molotov concerning Europe and Iran.[96] Following the World War II Anglo-Soviet invasion of Iran, the country was occupied by the Red Army in the far north and the British in the south. Iran was used by the United States and British to supply the Soviet Union, and the Allies agreed to withdraw from Iran within six months after the cessation of hostilities. However, when this deadline came, the Soviets remained in Iran under the guise of the Azerbaijan People's Government and Kurdish Republic of Mahabad. Shortly thereafter, on 5 March, former British prime minister Winston Churchill delivered his famous "Iron Curtain" speech in Fulton, Missouri. The speech called for an Anglo-

American alliance against the Soviets, whom he accused of establishing an "iron curtain" dividing Europe from "Stettin in the Baltic to Trieste in the Adriatic".

A week later, on 13 March, Stalin responded vigorously to the speech, saying that Churchill could be compared to Hitler insofar as he advocated the racial superiority of English-speaking nations so that they could satisfy their hunger for world domination, and that such a declaration was "a call for war on the USSR." The Soviet leader also dismissed the accusation that the USSR was exerting increasing control over the countries lying in its sphere. He argued that there was nothing surprising in "the fact that the Soviet Union, anxious for its future safety, [was] trying to see to it that governments loyal in their attitude to the Soviet Union should exist in these countries." Under President John F. Kennedy, US troop levels in Vietnam grew under the Military Assistance Advisory Group program from just under a thousand in 1959 to 16,000 in 1963.[0][P] South Vietnamese President Ngo Dinh Diem's heavy-handed crackdown on Buddhist monks in 1963 led the US to endorse a deadly military coup against Diem. The war escalated further in 1964 following the controversial Gulf of Tonkin incident, in which a US destroyer was alleged to have clashed with North Vietnamese fast attack craft. The Gulf of Tonkin Resolution gave President Lyndon B. Johnson broad authorization to increase US military presence, deploying ground combat units for the first time and increasing troop levels to 184,000.[280] Soviet leader Leonid Brezhnev responded by reversing Khrushchev's policy of disengagement and increasing aid to the North Vietnamese, hoping to entice the North from its pro-Chinese position. The USSR discouraged further escalation of the war, however, providing just enough military assistance to tie up American forces. From this point, the People's Army of Vietnam (PAVN), also known as the North Vietnamese Army (NVA), engaged in more conventional warfare with US and South Vietnamese forces.

The Western Bloc was led by the United States, as well as a number of other First World nations that were generally liberal democratic but tied to a network of often authoritarian Third World states, most of which were the European powers' former colonies.[3][B] The Eastern Bloc was led by the Soviet Union and its Communist Party, which had an influence across the Second World and was also tied to a network of authoritarian states. The Soviet Union had a command economy and installed similarly Communist regimes in its satellite states. United States involvement in regime change during the Cold War included support for anti-communist and right-wing dictatorships, governments, and uprisings

across the world, while Soviet involvement in regime change included the funding left-wing parties, wars of national liberation and revolutions around the world. As nearly all the colonial states underwent decolonization and achieved independence in the period from 1945 to 1960, many became Third World battlefields in the Cold War.

The Cold War is an international, military, technological, economic and ideological confrontation between the world from 1946 to the end of the 1980s. Block systems of different socio-economic states. The decisive factor of the war is the conflict between capitalist and socialist systems. Two superpowers tried to reshape the world according to its ideological principles. The decisive factor of the war is the conflict between capitalist and socialist systems. Two superpowers were ³at work. Rebuilding the world according to their ideological principles. The Cold War is a global geopolitical conflict. The USSR and its allies, on the one hand, and the USA and its allies, on the other, lasted from the mid-1940s to the early 1990s. On March 5, 1946, former British Prime Minister Winston Churchill gave a famous speech at Westminster College in Fulton (Missouri, USA) The Cold War began. One of the goals of the Marshall Plan was "unification". Europe, that is, the destruction of all currencies and customs, both within Europe itself and the barriers between Europe and the United States. In particular, he envisioned the unification of Ruhr coal and Lorraine, iron ore, and the creation of a single European market. According to some experts, the situation is somewhat reminiscent of the situation in the USSR during the NEP: the industry did not offer enough consumer goods to the market, and as a result, there was no incentive to increase production in agriculture. In addition, the winter of 1946-1947 was harsher. However, the government actually ignored this opinion. Most of the factions of the Finnish parliament (eduskunta), fearing a negative reaction from Moscow, as a result of ⁴which the Soviet side could ratify the peace treaty was delayed and calculations appeared to ease compensation payments. It would be impossible to do. Western European countries received aid under the Marshall Plan (except Spain), Turkey and Greece. The Soviet Union, Eastern European countries and Finland were excluded from the program. On June 5, 1947, George Marshall proposed the US Secretary of State Marshall Plan. Post-war Europe On June 5, 1947, US Secretary of State George Marshall offered Western Europe American assistance. Hostile

⁴ Service, Robert (2015). *The End of the Cold War: 1985–1991*. Macmillan. Miller, Nicola (2002). "The Real Gap in the Cuban Missile Crisis: The Post-Cold-War Historiography and Continued Omission of Cuba". In Carter, Dale; Clifton, Robin (eds.). Ekholm, Kai (2001). "Political Censorship in Finnish Libraries in 1944–1946". *Libraries & Culture*.

political and economic confrontation of the second half of the 20th century between the USSR and its satellite countries, on the one hand, and Western countries on the other. It was March 5, 1946, when former British Prime Minister Winston Churchill suggested that Europe was divided by the "Iron Curtain" in his Fulton speech (USA). Between the Soviet-occupied zone and the rest of Europe due to ideological differences. Since then, the term "Iron Curtain" has been used as a dividing line between the USSR and the influence of Western countries around the world. The USA and the USSR competed with each other, provoked or engaged in hostilities. Conflicts in different parts of the world, the creation of satellite regimes, seeking new allies, economic and political competition, and also exchanging reprimands to increase their own influence by reducing the influence of the other party. This competition supported the general political feeling of instability in the world until the end of the 1980s, the economy of the USSR could not withstand the competition and collapsed. The main characteristics of the Cold War were the arms race (this was especially true for weapons of mass destruction, for example, nuclear, hydrogen, chemical, etc.) and active propaganda. In any case, the country of the opposite bloc was represented as the Enemy, whose cultural and material values were defined as Alien and wrong. The third sign In some countries there are conflicts that can be called blocs that entered into real military conflicts in the territory of third countries (for example, in the Congo or Afghanistan).

Phases of the Cold War The first phase of the Cold War is the end of the 1940s and 1960s. - extreme Severity of conflict:

- Stalin's demands for revision of borders in Europe and Asia and the Black Sea Straits regime, regime change management of former Italian colonies in Africa;
- W. Churchill's March 1946 speech in Fulton. Protecting the Western world by all possible means with the appeal "The spread of the influence of the USSR";
- The Truman Doctrine (February 1947). Rescue measures from European Soviet expansion" (including the creation of a network). military bases near Soviet borders). The main doctrines are the doctrines of "containing" and "throwing back" Communism;
- Pro-Soviet bloc Eastern European countries created by the Soviet Union (based on local Communist parties and Soviet military bases), the proliferation of these countries is the Soviet model of development;
- "Iron Curtain", Stalin's dictatorship, domestic and foreign policy of countries of the Socialist camp, politics Purging, repression, execution. The height of the Cold War - 1949-1950:

- NATO, Council for Mutual Economic Assistance and Warsaw Pact organizations. The confrontation of two people Military-political blocs and the increase of weapons, including nuclear missiles;
- The Berlin crisis of the Federal Republic of Germany and the German Democratic Republic
- Conflicts and wars in Southeast Asia (Korea, Vietnam), in the Middle East, in which the USA and the USSR participated directly or indirectly. Cuban Missile Crisis 1962 (Peace on the Brink of a New World War);
The entry of the USSR troops in Czechoslovakia in 1968. The second stage of the Cold War - 1970s. - reduce international tension:
- Agreements between Germany and the USSR, Poland, East Germany. Czechoslovakia;
- West Berlin agreement, Soviet-American arms limitation agreements (ABM and SALT);
- Security and cooperation in Europe (attempts to live in peace) in Helsinki in 1975. Two systems, its complexity and contradictions);
- Military-political parity between the USSR and the USA. The third stage - late 1970s - mid-1980s:
- The end of the error, the new aggravation of the international situation, the confrontation between the two systems;
- Deterioration of Soviet-American relations, new era arms race, American SDI program;
- Increasing involvement of the United States in the politics of the Middle East and Latin America;
- Entry of Soviet troops into Afghanistan; "Brezhnev doctrine" - limitation of the sovereignty of the countries of the socialist camp; The friction increased within him;
- Attempts to continue the Cold War policy Crisis conditions of the world socialist system.

The official documentation of the end of the Cold War was implemented on November 21, 1990 with the adoption of the OSCE "Paris Charter" Meeting of Heads of State and Government for a New Europe" (signed by M. S. Gorbachev on behalf of the USSR). The Cold War ended with the disintegration of the USSR and the self-dissolution of the Warsaw Pact organizations. The main reason was the international situation that arose after the end of the Second World War. The United States has seen a dramatic rise in the political sphere. In Cuba, the 26th of July Movement, led by young revolutionaries Fidel Castro and Che Guevara,

seized power in the Cuban Revolution on 1 January 1959, toppling President Fulgencio Batista, whose unpopular regime had been denied arms by the Eisenhower administration.[248] Although Fidel Castro's first refused to categorize his new government as socialist and repeatedly denying being a communist, Castro appointed Marxists to senior government and military positions. Most significantly, Che Guevara became Governor of the Central Bank and then Minister of Industries.

Diplomatic relations between Cuba and the United States continued for some time after Batista's fall, but President Eisenhower deliberately left the capital to avoid meeting Castro during the latter's trip to Washington, D.C. in April, leaving Vice President Richard Nixon to conduct the meeting in his place.[250] Cuba began negotiating for arms purchases from the Eastern Bloc in March 1960.[251] The same month, Eisenhower gave approval to CIA plans and funding to overthrow Castro. In January 1961, just prior to leaving office, Eisenhower formally severed relations with the Cuban government. That April, the administration of newly elected American President John F. Kennedy mounted the unsuccessful CIA-organized ship-borne invasion of the island by Cuban exiles at Playa Girón and Playa Larga in Santa Clara Province—a failure that publicly humiliated the United States.[253] Castro responded by publicly embracing Marxism–Leninism, and the Soviet Union pledged to provide further support.[253] In December, the US government began a campaign of terrorist attacks against Cuba and covert operations and sabotage against the administration, in an attempt to overthrow the Castro regime.

In the course of the 1960s and 1970s, Cold War participants struggled to adjust to a new, more complicated pattern of international relations in which the world was no longer divided into two clearly opposed blocs.[120] From the beginning of the post-war period, with American help Western Europe and Japan rapidly recovered from the destruction of World War II and sustained strong economic growth through the 1950s and 1960s, with per capita GDPs approaching those of the United States, while Eastern Bloc economies stagnated. The Vietnam War descended into a quagmire for the United States, leading to a decline in international prestige and economic stability, derailing arms agreements, and provoking domestic unrest. America's withdrawal from the war led it to embrace a policy of détente with both China and the Soviet Union. In the 1973 oil crisis, Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) cut their petroleum output. This raised oil prices and hurt Western

economies, but helped the Soviet Union by generating a huge flow of money from its oil sales.

As a result of the oil crisis, combined with the growing influence of Third World alignments such as OPEC and the Non-Aligned Movement, less powerful countries had more room to assert their independence and often showed themselves resistant to pressure from either superpower.[182] Meanwhile, Moscow was forced to turn its attention inward to deal with the Soviet Union's deep-seated domestic economic problems.[120] During this period, Soviet leaders such as Leonid Brezhnev and Alexei Kosygin embraced the notion of détente.

References:

1. Service, Robert (2015). *The End of the Cold War: 1985–1991*. Macmillan.
2. Miller, Nicola (2002). "The Real Gap in the Cuban Missile Crisis: The Post-Cold-War Historiography and Continued Omission of Cuba". In Carter, Dale; Clifton, Robin (eds.).
3. Ekholm, Kai (2001). "Political Censorship in Finnish Libraries in 1944–1946". *Libraries & Culture*.
4. Benjamin M. Weissman, "Herbert Hoover and the famine in Soviet Russia, 1921-23" in Mark Hatfield, ed. *Herbert Hoover Reassessed* (1981) pp 390–396.
5. Breslauer, George W. (2002). *Gorbachev and Yeltsin as Leaders*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Blumberg, Arnold (1995). *Great Leaders, Great Tyrants?: Contemporary Views of World Rulers Who Made History*. Westport, Connecticut: Greenwood Press.
7. Chandler, David (2000). *Brother Number One: A Political Biography of Pol Pot, Revised Edition*. Chiang Mai, Thailand: Silkworm Books.
8. Umidovich A. B., Alibek A. AUTONOMY OF TURKESTAN AND ITS ACTIVITY //Web of Humanities: Journal of Social Science and Humanitarian Research. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 79-82.
9. Rahimova F., Asatov A. Schools and education in Central Asia in the late XIX th and early XX th centuries //International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 72-75.
10. Asatov A. Jadidist movement in Turkestan Struggle for people's spirituality //International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 80-82.

